

NESCent External funding

Since January of 2006 NESCent has applied for, and has received the following grants beyond the core NESCent grant.

A. Funded

A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology

National Science Foundation, BD&I (PI: Kathleen Smith, Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$1,907,531

NESCent Total Amount: \$2,180,169

09/01/2008 – 08/31/2012

Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource

National Science Foundation, CCLI (PI: Kathleen Smith, Kristin Jenkins)

Total Direct Costs: \$117,976

Total Amount: \$150,000

01/01/2009 – 12/31/2010

INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)

National Science Foundation (PIs: Kathleen Smith and Hilmar Lapp)

NESCent Total Direct: \$39,535

NESCent Total Amount: \$50,803

07/15/2008 – 06/30/2011

Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering (HIVE)

Subagreement through UNC – Chapel Hill ((PI: J. Greenberg)

Institute for Museum and Library Sciences (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Amount: cost share only to Duke University

1/1/2009 – 6/30/2011

Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies

Subaward through University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)

National Science Foundation BDI-0641025 (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$853,338

NESCent Total Amount: \$1,050,945

06/01/2007 - 5/31/2010

Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)

National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$242,565

NESCent Total Amount: \$310,482 (D&I to UNC),

4/1/2007 - 3/31/2010

Development of the www.EcoliCommunity.org Information Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)

National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$30,550

NESCent Total Amount: \$39,104

06/01/2007 – 05/31/2009

B. In Review

DataNetONE: Observation Network for Earth

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: W. Michener)

National Science Foundation (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Direct: \$390,490

NESCent Total Amount: \$501,780

10/1/2008 – 9/30/2013